

Local Public Administration's Role in Multidimensional Poverty and Human Rights Violations in Brazil: Insights from Botuporã

Edérson Dos Santos Alves

Law Professor, University Málaga

Co-Author

Luis Renato Vedovato, Universidade Estadual de Campinas (Unicamp)

This study investigates the role of local public administration in perpetuating multidimensional poverty and human rights violations in small municipalities, focusing on Botuporã, Bahia, Brazil. Utilizing the consensual approach to multidimensional poverty developed by Joanna Mack and Stewart Lansley (1985), which is based on Peter Townsend's theory of relative deprivation (1979), the research analyzes data from seven focus groups conducted in Botuporã in 2022. These discussions reveal a widespread consensus on unmet basic needs such as clean water, reliable transportation, healthcare, and education. Quantitative analysis using QoG and V-Dem datasets highlights correlations between weak governance indicators—such as low government effectiveness and transparency—and increased multidimensional poverty levels. Comparative insights from Latin America and Europe further emphasize the global relevance of these findings. The study concludes that centralized decision-making, inadequate infrastructure, and a lack of accountability mechanisms disproportionately impact marginalized populations, particularly those in peripheral areas. Policy recommendations include decentralizing administrative power, enhancing transparency, and prioritizing targeted investments in mobility and service delivery to ensure equitable access to fundamental rights enshrined in international frameworks such as Agenda 2030 and Habitat III.

Keywords: Multidimensional poverty, local public administration, human rights violations, consensual approach, transparency.